

ISic3644

I.Sicily inscription 3644

Language

Sikel

Type

terminus (?)

Material

volcanic

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mendolito

Place of origin (modern)

Mendolito

Provenance

proprieta Sanfilippo, Mendolito (Long 14.80968; Lat 37.70611)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Adrano, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Adrano

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Manganaro, G. 1961. Iscrizioni di Adrano in alfabeto siculo. *Archeologia Classica*. 13: 106-112.

Albanese, R.M. 1991. Mendolito. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G.(eds.), *Bibliografia topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle isole tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 545-561. At 545 no.1

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